

The church/(mosque) of Transfiguration of Savior, at Niokastro, Pylos, south-western Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece

Secondary source

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The building currently used as the Church of the Transfiguration of the Savior at Niokastro castle, in Pylos, south-western Messinia, is one of the largest preserved examples of muslim and christian religious place in the post-medieval Peloponnese. It was first build as mosque during Murad III's sultan reign (1574 and 1595), then it was transformed into a catholic church under the Venetian rule (1686-1715) dedicated to saint Vito, and finally today orthodox christian ritual is performed at the feast day of Transfiguration of Christ. The building shares features of ottoman and post-byzantine architecture such as the portico, the eight-sided dome, the mihrabs, the minaret, the islamic arches. It is square in ground plan, with four large pillars carrying the central dome, and four barrel vaults that radiate cruciformly from it.

Date Range: 1570 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Greece

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Greece

Niokastro, Pylos, south-western Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1:

<https://www.efames.gr/assets/%ce%bd%ce%b9%ce%bf%ce%ba%ce%b1%cf%83%cf%84%cf%81%ce%bf-2019-3ptyxo.pdf>

Notes: see also bibliography

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL:

<https://www.efames.gr/assets/%ce%bd%ce%b9%ce%bf%ce%ba%ce%b1%cf%83%cf%84%cf%81%ce%bf-2019-3ptyxo.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=it_Aa8kgISk (an orthodox christian ritual performed at the building)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: by staff of the local Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia, the Public Archaeological Service of the Greek Ministry of Culture

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1999-2002

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Restoration (and excavation) of Transfiguration of Christ church at Niokastro, Pylos

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Other [specify]: arid hill and close to a port

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: several and various built structures

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: the small city of Pylos

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: the building is included within the fortification walls of Niokastro castle

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The Niokastro castle, where the building is situated, is on the route from Pylos to Methoni

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: there are other churches within the city of Pylos

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Clearing

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: also, several transformations took place that altered significantly and repeatedly the building's initial form and architecture

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Christ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Other [specify]: sultan (Murat III), then the local Venetian authorities, finally orthodox christian Greeks

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:
– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: of different ethnicities: Ottoman Turks, Venetian, Greeks

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: it was initially sponsored by the central ottoman administration in Constantinople

↳

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: it was built by the Ottoman Turks, now belongs to Greek state

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: mainly water structures: ducts, cisterns, collectors

↳

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: land clearings

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: there are ruins of nearby structures of secular character

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: presumably, the building had the leading role in the wider area of the castle since it was the main religious place.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: However, the building is impressive in its architecture

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Earth

– Yes

Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Sand

– Yes

Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: brick, typical element of ottoman and post byzantine architecture

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: built and hewn

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: modern-day religious icons placed on the wooden templon screen

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Notes: there are inscriptions but play the role of commemoration/dedication

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: brick decoration bands

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Initially, no, but afterwards burials were found inside the building. They were probably carried out when the building lost its initial worship character.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: beneath the floor of the building

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: the local Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia and the Ephorate of Underwater Antiquities (both Public Services of Greek Ministry of Culture) are responsible for the maintenance of the place/building

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: inside the building

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: once or twice a year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: orthodox christian priests

↳ Present full time
– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: at the commemoration day of prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: strictly and only male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Greek

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: they are orthodox christian priests

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia, Public Archaeological Service of Greek Ministry of Culture

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: only once or twice a year

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: subterranean cisterns, surface collectors, ducts running from the roof

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The church/(mosque) of Transfiguration of Savior, at Niokastro, Pylos, south-western Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece, Kontogiannis, Nikos. "From Mosque to Church and Back Again: Investigating a House of Faith in Post-medieval Pylos, 771-856". *Hesperia* 84 (January 1, 2015).